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Effectiveness of Pyrethrum Dosage on Maize and Bean Weevils under Farmer's Storage Conditions in Morogoro Region, Tanzania

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4.1 Abstract

Storage of grains is essential in agriculture, both to initiate new life and from a food security point of view. Recently, farmers have been encouraged to use different botanical insecticides instead of synthetic insecticides because of the many problems associated with synthetic chemicals. A field study was conducted at the ten selected farmer's stores in Morogoro, Tanzania, from November 2020 to May 2021 to evaluate the effect of pyrethrum dosage on maize and bean weevils under farmers' storage conditions. Pyrethrum powder at six dosage levels (5, 10, 15, 20, 25, and 30 g/kg) was mixed with 1 kg of disinfested maize and bean grains in separate polythene bags, and the effects on insect mortality, grain damage, and weight loss were assessed.

The results showed that there was significant difference only in the highest concentration (20 g/kg and 25 g/kg for bean and maize grains respectively) pyrethrum and the control ($P < 0.05$). Grain weight loss in pyrethrum powder-treated grains was dose-dependent, ranging from 0% in the highest dose to 26.49 and 46.52 % in beans and maize grains, respectively, in the control, with significant differences. Generally, the powders are cheap and safer for human consumption hence is recommended to be used as maize and bean protectants in storage. Further studies on the packaging and sales of these plant powders for easy accessibility to farmers and consumers of maize is also suggested.

Keywords: Maize grains; bean grains; chemical control; pyrethrum powder; maize weevils; bean weevil

4.2 Introduction

Grain storage is important for food security and the beginning of new life in agriculture (Lal *et al.*, 2017). The prevention of losses, which are primarily imposed on weevils, beetles, moths, and rodents, is also greatly assisted by storage (Kartikeyan *et al.*, 2009). 60–70% of the food grain produced in the country is reportedly stored in household storage facilities made of local materials. In general, smallholder farmers store grains for three main purposes: as food until the next season; as seed; and for selling when prices become reasonably high enough to benefit the farmer. Maize and bean weevils are among the storage insects that cause maize and bean grain loss in storage areas, which are throughout the world, because they reduce the quantity and quality of grain. In the temperate zone, they might cause 5–10% damage to grains that have been kept, whereas in the tropical zone, it might be 20–30% (Nakakita, 1998). In countries where modern storage technologies have not been introduced, damage may comprise 40% of the total (Shaaya *et al.*, 1997).

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In Tanzania, as in other countries in sub-Saharan Africa, it is estimated that between 25 and 40 percent of grain crops are lost to insect pests during storage every year due to inadequate village-level storage caused by poor storage structures and expensive and scarcely available storage of chemical insecticides (Koono and Njoya, 2004). Insect pests reduce the weight and quality of stored grains in addition to damaging them (Rayhan, 2014). Nowadays, synthetic insecticides are the mainstay of insect pest control technologies (Azad *et al.*, 2013).

Since the DDT discovery in 1939, synthetic insecticides have dominated insect pest management initiatives around the world (Misra, 2014). Synthetic product protectants have been linked to a number of problems, despite the fact that success in insect pest management has been achieved to a huge extent (Isman, 2006). Alternative approaches are required to minimize the use of these chemicals due to issues including residue accumulation in the grains and other side effects (Baker *et al.*, 2002; Gusmao *et al.*, 2013; Kemabonta and Odebiyi, 2005). Botanical insecticides have been confidently used since they are believed to be safer for the environment, normally less expensive, easily processed, and used by farmers and small industries (Belmain *et al.*, 2001; Habib *et al.*, 2011). Therefore, the aim of this research was to evaluate the effect of pyrethrum dosage on maize and bean weevils under farmers' storage conditions.

4.3 Materials and Methods

4.3.1 Experimental site

The experiment was conducted at Morogoro Municipal in ten selected farmer's stores, and each farmer's store was considered a replicate.

4.3.2 Materials

4.3.2.1 Plant materials

Pyrethrum flowers from TARI-Uyole in the Mbeya region were dried for seven days in the shade to prevent the active components from being destroyed by heat and light. Then, the dried flowers were ground with a microplant grinding machine and sieved through a 0.25mm more-size mesh sieve to obtain uniform fine dust particles (Araya, and Eman, 2009; Jembere *et al.*, 2005).

4.3.2.2 The grains materials

The maize grains (Staha variety) and bean grains (Kablanketi) were bought from smallholder farmers. The harvested grains had no history of insecticide treatment.

4.3.3 Methods

4.3.3.1 Experimental procedure

One kilogramme of both maize and bean grain samples in polythene bags for each treatment was used. The grain samples were treated with six different doses of 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, and 3.0% (w/w) of the products, i.e., 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, and 30 g of powders to 1 kg of the grains. Negative (untreated) and positive (treated with Actellic Super Dust (0.3% permethrin and 1.6% pirimiphos methyl) were applied at the recommended rate) controls were also included in the tests. The samples were stored in ten selected farmer's stores, and each farmer's store was considered one replication. The grain samples were not artificially infested with insects, and the infestation was expected to occur naturally from the insect population existing in the store or from the field as the test insects carried over. The samples were stored for 180 days.

4.4 Experimental Design

Treatments were arranged in a randomized complete block design (RCBD) and replicated ten times.

4.5 Data Collection

During this period, observations on the number of undamaged and damaged grains due to weevils were made at 30-day intervals. On each assessment date (30, 60, 90, 120, 150, and 180 days after treatment), the bags were

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opened, and the number of damaged and undamaged grains was determined by taking three random samples of 100 grains per replication in each treatment.

In addition, percentage mortality, percentage of damaged grains, and weight losses were calculated using the following formula:

1. Percentage damage (%D)

$$\text{Grain Damage (\%)} = \frac{Nd}{TNG} \times 100$$

Where: Nd = number of damaged grains and TNG : total number of grains

2. Percentage weight loss (Adams and Schulten, 1978).

$$\text{Weight loss (\%)} = \frac{\{(Wu \times Nd) - (Wd \times Nu)\}}{Wu \times (Nd \times Nu)} \times 100$$

Where: WL = Weight loss, Wu = Weight of undamaged grain, Nu = Number of undamaged grain, Wd = Weight of damaged grain, and Nd = Number of damaged grain.

4.6 Statistical Analysis

Collected data on damaged grains, undamaged grains, the weight of damaged grains, and the weight of undamaged grains were organized using Microsoft Excel and subjected to an analysis of variance (ANOVA) using GenStat (15th Edition) at a significance level of 5%. The mean separation was done using the Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT).

A Statistical Model for Completely Randomized Design (CRD)

$$Y_{ij} = \mu + \tau_i + P_i + \epsilon_{ij}$$

Where; μ = grand mean, τ_i = treatment affect and ϵ_{ij} = experimental error

4.7 Results

4.7.1 Percentage damage to bean grains and time of exposures

The results on percentage damage showed highly significant differences ($P < 0.05$) among the treatment doses applied (Table 4.1). Among treatment doses, the highest percentage of damage was recorded in the untreated bag at 180 days after treatment, while the lowest percentage of damage was observed from treatment with high doses, i.e., 3% (w/w) at 30, 60, 90, and 120 days after treatment. It was also observed for synthetic insecticides (Actellic Super Dust) (Table 4.1). 20 g/kg of pyrethrum dose was not significantly different from 25 g/kg and 30 g/kg pyrethrum doses and those of synthetic insecticides (Actellic Super Dust).

Table 4.1: Percentage damage of bean grains due to emerged bean weevils

Treatments (g/kg)	Grain damage (%)					
	30 Days	60 Days	90 Days	120 Days	150 Days	180 Days
Control(-)	5.1 a	22.0 a	45.0 a	68.4 a	75.0 a	97.3 a
5	3.9 b	10.8 b	22.6 b	45.1 b	66.9 b	70.5 b
10	2.8 c	5.8 c	10.8 c	22.6 c	43.8 c	44.6 c
15	1.6 d	3.7 d	5.8 d	10.0 d	22.6 d	22.5 d
20	0.3 e	0.9 e	1.4 e	1.7 e	10.0 e	10.1 e
25	0.1 e	0.3 ef	0.5 ef	0.5 f	6.0 f	7.4 f
30	0.0 e	0.0 f	0.0 f	0.0 f	4.3 g	5.1 g
Control(+)	0.0 e	0.0 f	0.0 f	0.0 f	0.4 h	1.0 h
Grand Mean	1.725	5.44	10.76	18.54	28.62	32.31
LSD	0.3302	0.823	0.945	0.991	1.159	1.152
CV%	21.4	16.9	9.8	6	4.5	4
F. Prob.	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001

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Means followed by the same letter(s) in the same columns are not significantly different according to DMRT ($P < 0.05$)

Control (-) and Control (+), untreated and treated with synthetic insecticides (Actellic super dust) at the recommended rate.

4.7.2 Percentage damage of maize grains and time of exposures

The results regarding percentage damage demonstrated highly significant differences ($P < 0.05$) among the treatment doses administered (Table 4.2). The untreated bag had the most damaged grains among the treatment dosages at 180 days, whereas treatment with high doses—3% (w/w) at 30, 60, 90, and 120 days—showed the least amount of grain damage. It was also observed for synthetic insecticides (Actellic Super Dust) (Table 4.2). 25 g/kg of pyrethrum dose was not significantly different from 30 g/kg of pyrethrum dose and those of synthetic insecticides (Actellic Super Dust).

Table 4.2: Percentage damage of maize grains due to emerged maize weevils

Treatments (g/kg)	Grain damage (%)					
	30 Days	60 Days	90 Days	120 Days	150 Days	180 Days
Control(-)	3.6 a	10.9 a	53.4 a	80.2 a	98.1 a	99.0 a
5	2.6 b	7.7 b	26.2 b	42.8 b	80.7 b	85.1 b
10	1.8 c	4.3 c	13.8 c	28.2 c	59.7 c	66.4 c
15	1.1 d	2.7 d	6.3 d	11.6 d	23.2 d	46.3 d
20	0.3 e	1.5 e	2.6 e	6.9 e	10.1 e	11.9 e
25	0.1 e	0.6 f	0.7 f	1.2 f	1.7 f	1.8 f
30	0.0 e	0.4 f	0.2 f	0.4 f	0.8 fg	0.9 fg
Control(+)	0.0 e	0.0 f	0.0 f	0.0 f	0.0 h	0.0 g
Grand Mean	1.188	3.513	12.9	21.41	34.29	38.92
LSD	0.3182	0.6207	0.985	1.161	1.299	1.105
CV%	30	19.8	8.5	6.1	4.2	3.2
F. Prob.	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001

Means followed by the same letter(s) in the same columns are not significantly different according to DMRT ($P < 0.05$). Control (-) and Control (+), untreated and treated with synthetic insecticides (Actellic super dust) at the recommended rate

4.7.3 Weight loss of bean grains and time of exposures

The results on percentage weight loss indicated highly significant differences ($P < 0.05$) among the treatment doses applied (Fig. 4.1). Among treatment doses, the highest percentage of weight loss was recorded in the untreated bag at 180 days after treatment, while the lowest percentage of weight loss was observed from treatment with high doses, i.e., 3% (w/w) at 30, 60, 90, and 120 days. It was also observed for synthetic insecticides (Actellic Super Dust) (Fig. 4.1). 20 g/kg of pyrethrum dose was not significantly different from 25 g/kg, 30 g/kg of pyrethrum dose, and those of synthetic insecticides (Actellic Super Dust).

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Figure 4.1: Percentage weight loss of bean at different doses

4.7.4 Weight loss of maize grains and time of exposures

The findings on percentage weight loss revealed highly significant differences ($P < 0.05$) between the various treatment doses used (Fig. 4.2). Among treatment doses, the highest percentage of weight loss was recorded in the untreated bag at 180 days, while the lowest percentage of weight loss was observed from treatment with high doses, i.e., 3% (w/w) at 30, 60, 90, and 120 days after treatment. It was also observed for synthetic insecticides (Actellic Super Dust) (Fig. 4.2). 25 g/kg of pyrethrum dose was not significantly different from 30 g/kg of pyrethrum dose and those of synthetic insecticides (Actellic Super Dust).

Figure 4.2: Percentage weight loss of maize at different doses

4.8 Discussion

The result of the present study revealed that the flower powders of pyrethrum could serve as a poison against adult maize and bean weevils. The mortality of maize and bean weevils in the maize and bean grains, respectively, treated with various concentrations of pyrethrum flower powder was found to be dose-dependent. The result of the study further showed that the mortality of maize and bean weevils caused by the various concentrations of the different flower powders used was higher than that of the control (untreated treatments). The population of maize and bean weevils in the experiment was significantly reduced by the pyrethrum insecticides. This indicated that the flower powders were poisonous to adult maize and bean weevils and could serve as a bioinsecticide. The insecticidal activity of pyrethrum (Mulungu *et al.*, 2007) is primarily due to

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pyrethrins (Shivanandappa and Rajashelar, 2014) and might be the cause of the insecticidal activity in this study. Researchers have reported that pyrethrum has insecticidal properties (Wanyika *et al.*, 2009).

This result was similar to those of Mulungu *et al.* (2007), Wanyika (2009), and Shiberi and Negeri (2014), mainly due to the fact that the pyrethrins are very fast killers of the target insect pests because of their mode of action and low resistance to target insect pests (Saeed *et al.*, 2012). The results in relation to time and dose were similar to those of Pugazhvendan *et al.* (2009), as they used some plant parts with insecticidal and repellent activities, and they showed effectiveness as the doses were increased over a longer period of time.

In the early stages, the botanicals were equally effective. This shows that the efficacy of botanicals against storage insect pests is high during the early application phase and probably decreases with time. This might be a result of botanical insecticides degrading chemically while being stored for a long time. Reducing the number of insect offspring produced in the treated grains is one of the essential qualities of an efficient grain protectant. In laboratory studies (controlled conditions), *C. cinerariifolium* dramatically reduced the progeny emergence of maize and bean weevils by more than 40%.

In contrast, *C. cinerariifolium* reduced the emergence of progeny by a greater percentage in our study. In the same way, *C. cinerariifolium* decreased grain damage and weight loss under the farmer's storage conditions by preventing the progeny of maize weevils from emerging from the re-infestation.

As a result, the adult completely perished without laying any eggs in the bags; however, when the control treatment was inspected five weeks after treatment, substantial egg-laying occurred. This discrepancy in emergence is likely caused by the fact that maize and bean weevils lay their eggs inside the grain and that the powder does not sufficiently penetrate the grain coat to destroy the eggs inside. After six months of storage, significant grain damage and weight loss were noticed among the treatments in comparison to the untreated control (Tables 4.1 and 4.2 and Figs. 4.3 and 4.4). Compared to the untreated control, all treatments reduced grain damage and weight loss. Treatments with high doses (i.e., 20, 25, and 30 g/kg) showed less grain damage and weight loss than the standard control.

Synthetic insecticides are very fast killers of the target insect pests and can give excellent control when they are treated. However, in stored grains, these insecticides have some lethal effects or have toxic residues, which can harm consumers. Therefore, this study was conducted to give the idea of alternative use of these botanicals for replacement of these insecticides in storage and stored grains to minimize the toxic effects of insecticides. So pyrethrum is less toxic for human consumption and can give excellent control of insect insect pests, particularly maize and bean weevils. Testing these in two different ways for their efficacy was to check the best possible way to use them in the stored grains for insect pest control, as pyrethrum was found to be the best for insect pest control.

4.9 Conclusion

Consequently, protecting our food from storage insects is a priority to ensure food security. The treatments decreased maize and bean weevil reproduction, grain weight loss, grain damage (holes in grains), and increased mortality. No loss of weight or perforations of holes were observed on treated maize grains. However, untreated grains sustained huge weight loss and the greatest number of offspring and holes. As the amount of pyrethrum dosage applied increased, the rate of insect emergence was affected, unlike that of untreated grains, which does not have a negative impact on the rate of insect emergence of maize and bean weevils. Generally, pyrethrum flower powder treatments were found to be effective against the attack of maize and bean weevils. This provides good arguments for carrying out this study on natural insecticides. Thus, the tested products could serve as potential tools for the management of storage insect pests. Future efforts should focus on product optimization, packaging, and marketing.

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